

Neurological Conditions and Creativity: Memory and Creativity

Abstract

The purpose of this literature review is to elucidate the relationship between painting and dementia within the context of art as a form of human communication originating from symbolic cognition. This form of communication serves to convey ideas, experiences, and emotions. It is imperative to acknowledge that individuals afflicted with neurodegenerative disorders invariably encounter behavioral and cognitive impairments, which pose potential restrictions on the artist's capacity to fully manifest their creative and expressive intentions through the medium of painting. In this respect, this article explores the remarkable career of Willem de Kooning, the Dutch-born artist widely recognized as the "father of abstract expressionism," who was also diagnosed with Alzheimer's disease. The article examines the factors that enabled him to produce paintings at an accelerated rate despite the challenges posed by the condition, in order to enhance our comprehension of the cognitive processes involved in artistic expression. The interdisciplinary research fields propose an approach that entails the delineation and examination of the impacted neural areas and their resultant effects on artistic output.

Keywords

Dementia, Alzheimer's Disease, Willem de Kooning, Art, Fronto-Temporal Dementia, Visual Art, Neurodegeneration

In the fields of neuroscience, neuropsychology, and neurology, the relationship between brain structures and their functions is typically deduced from observing the behavioral consequences of damage in specific brain regions. Previous knowledge regarding the impact of brain damage on artistic abilities primarily stems from studies conducted on visual artists. Artistic production involves various cognitive processes, and dementia has been found to have predictable effects on art. Degenerative dementias affect specific brain regions, with differences in neuroanatomy. In individuals with Alzheimer's disease, the temporoparietal lobes are initially affected, leading to deficits in processing perceptual and spatial information. As a result, these individuals are less likely to initiate or complete artistic projects. When they do continue to create art, they tend to simplify their work and focus on a restricted range of topics. This increased abstraction is not a sign of creativity but rather a result of the loss of ability to recognize relationships between structures and shapes. It is important to note that there is no evidence to suggest that new art habits develop after the onset of Alzheimer's disease. The effect of neurodegenerative diseases on artistic production is contingent upon the level of cognitive, behavioral, and motor dysfunction. Current medical literature has documented cases of artists with dementia who continue to engage in painting activities. Studies involving patients with dementia and other brain injuries have contributed to our understanding of the role played by different brain areas in the creation of art, as well as the essence of visual creativity itself. The analysis of drawings made by patients with dementia offers a unique opportunity to examine the consequences of brain damage on artistic abilities. Previous studies have documented a decline in artistic skills, particularly in professional artists, as the disease advances, leading to the eventual cessation of painting. However, there have also been cases where individuals with severe dementia have been

able to preserve their artistic abilities. Patients with Alzheimer's Disease often experience impairments in visuo-constructive, linguistic, and musical skills. According to Gretton et al., in the early stages of the disease, the art of individuals with AD is characterized by significant changes in the quality of spatial construction and, to a lesser extent, visual perceptual attributes such as color and contrast. These changes are primarily attributed to a reduction in planning ability, resulting in a simplification of artistic style. Case reports of artists with Alzheimer's Disease have demonstrated a decline in their ability to accurately represent subject matter in a realistic manner. Instead, they tend to rely on copying their previous artistic creations and abandoning their previous styles. This shift towards more abstract representations is likely a result of the distortion of global visuospatial aspects of the image caused by right parietal involvement in Alzheimer's Disease. In 1996, UCSF behavioral neurologist Bruce Miller, MD, identified that visual creativity is occasionally seen in patients with Frontotemporal Dementia, which is a progressive neurodegenerative disease that primarily affects the frontal and anterior temporal lobes. Some patients with this type of dementia actually experience an improvement in artistic skills after the onset of their illness. Despite being socially impaired and cognitively compromised, these individuals may become preoccupied with the fine details of faces, objects, and shapes. While most artists with frontotemporal dementia experience aphasia, they retain functioning in the posterior parietotemporal regions, especially in the non-dominant hemisphere, which sets them apart from those with Alzheimer's disease. Patients with FTD often exhibit simpler compositions in their drawings, and their copying and collage skills are typically poor and completed quickly. They also tend to alter proportions in relation to the model, using more muted and cold colors and including fewer details. Due to executive dysfunction, patients demonstrate deficits in attention, abstraction, planning, and problem-solving, while language, memory, and visuospatial ability are relatively preserved. Some patients with frontal dementia exhibit a simplification of drawing and an increased attention to detail. Painters with FTD and predominant left hemisphere dysfunction often lose their ability for abstraction and symbolic representation, but their paintings can appear more emotional and creative.

Also, a group of brain disorders shares similar clinical features. In semantic dementia, a subtype of frontotemporal dementia, hypometabolism of the left anterior temporal lobe may release the visually oriented right hemisphere. This aligns with theories of paradoxical functional facilitation, which suggest that changes in inhibition and brain plasticity can lead to compensatory augmentation of sensory and perceptual functions. These brain disorders include behavioral variant FTD, semantic dementia, and progressive non-fluent aphasia. Semantic dementia is characterized by difficulties in naming, single-word comprehension, and verbal fluency, as well as a loss of common knowledge about objects. Progressive non-fluent aphasia is characterized by non-fluent speech with deficits in lexical, phonological, and syntactic abilities. Bv-FTD typically manifests as behavior and psychopathological changes. These different variants of FTD share spared visual perceptual abilities until later stages of the disease, which means that aspects of art such as spatial relations, contrast, and color remain unaffected.

Additionally, the personality of the patients has various manifestations. The patient's personality can remain intact in some form, provided the patient is given an outlet or opportunity to express it. In Willem de Kooning's case, it is possible to identify and compare some de novo and onset dementia behavior patterns.

Willem de Kooning, regarded by his contemporaries as the leader of the New York avant-garde movement, distinctly represented an artist's artist, in sharp contrast to the more publicly renowned Jackson Pollock. Born into a financially constrained household in Rotterdam, de Kooning underwent training in fine and commercial arts at the Rotterdam Academy. In 1926, the artist embarked on a daring escapade by sneaking onto a ship destined for Argentina, subsequently seizing an opportunity during the vessel's stay in Virginia to evade immigration authorities and establish himself in New Jersey, thereby marking the commencement of his lifelong artistic journey. In his new surroundings, de Kooning took on employment as a house painter, inadvertently exposing himself to the use of large brushes and fluid paints, tools that would extensively remain central to his creative pursuits. Furthermore, his mastery in drawing and craftsmanship provided an indispensable basis for the entirety of his artistic output, even encompassing his most abstract paintings. De Kooning established his artistic career in New York, where he was captivated by the expressive freedom of jazz and the abstract art created by fellow artists under its influence. The city also introduced him to the art of Henri Matisse as well as influential contemporaries like John Graham and Arshile Gorky, with whom he formed a close and inspirational friendship.

In the 1930s, the Great Depression marked the end of the Jazz Age, and de Kooning participated in the Works Progress Administration program, collaborating with Fernand Léger on public mural designs. Although these murals were never realized, they were pivotal in his development as an artist and encouraged him to pursue art full-time. Throughout his long artistic career, spanning nearly seven decades, de Kooning explored a diverse range of styles, ultimately solidifying his position as an essential link between New York School painting and European modernism. His creative process was characterized by extensive physical labor and numerous revisions, encompassing both abstract and figurative elements. Particularly controversial were his portrayals of the female figure, which garnered significant debate during his lifetime and continue to be subjects of discussion today.

In the late 1940s and early 1950s, Willem de Kooning gained widespread recognition for his paintings in the "Woman" series, reaching the peak of his fame.

Figure 1. "Woman" by Willem de Kooning, 1952

(From the Collection of Thomas B. Hess, Gift of the heirs of Thomas B. Hess, 1984, © 2023

Artists Rights Society (ARS), New York)

He was also associated with prominent artists such as Jackson Pollack, Mark Rothko, Matisse, Picasso, and Gorky. Besides, de Kooning's paintings can be likened to the experimental jazz and bebop music that were popular during his peak years.

The only thing that hasn't changed in the life of Willem de Kooning was change. de Kooning had a tendency to periodically reinvent himself, creating new styles that differed from his previous works. However, he would also incorporate elements from his past and modify his techniques without completely abandoning them. This restlessness and drive to innovate contributed to his status as a renowned artist in the 20th century.

According to Gary Garrels on Willem de Kooning: The Late Paintings, *"Throughout his career, de Kooning periodically would reinvent himself, developing a new style that was seemingly removed from, even at odds with, what had immediately come before. Yet just as characteristically he would double back—taking some-thing from his own past, recombining elements, altering but not abandoning techniques, changing but not rupturing his practice."*¹

In his later years, de Kooning struggled with alcohol abuse and suffered from malnourishment and physical weakness. He turned to alcohol to combat insomnia, which he attributed to anxiety attacks. During this time, he would often roam the city throughout the night. In the 1950s, de Kooning and his wife, Elaine, supported de Kooning in his efforts to overcome his alcoholism, improve his diet, and take better care of himself. While successful, this period was followed by a two-year episode of severe depression during which de Kooning experienced alternating periods of withdrawal and rage.

After de Kooning achieved sobriety, he experienced a serious bout of depression. This was accompanied by a recurrence of the anxiety attacks that initially led him to drink, as well as physical changes due to not consuming alcohol anymore and taking tranquilizers like valium to control his intense fits of rage. These fits of rage typically occurred at night, resembling a condition known as "Sundowning Syndrome" where individuals with dementia often exhibit sudden changes in mood or restlessness during the evening.

In his 70's, which is when his disease was probably began, friends and family were noticing his forgetfulness. He forgot recent events, name of the people, replaced his confusion with silences, or covered up his confusion with confabulation or wisecracks which is reminiscent of his clever sense of humor and he reported to have episodes of rage against his apparently faltering memory, which subsided as the disease progressed, a common phenomenon in those with dementia. Yet, he remembered details of his education in Rotterdam, his illegal immigration to the United States, his job as a house painter and his struggles in developing his art in New York. And, in his late 80's, de Kooning was diagnosed with Alzheimer's. When all behavioral, cognitive and physical changes of de Kooning considered, his dementia probably had several etiologies such as

¹ Garrels G: *Willem de Kooning: The Late Paintings, the 1980's*. San Francisco, CA: San Francisco Museum of Modern Art, 1996.

arteriosclerosis, alcoholism, Korsakoff's syndrome, uncertain nutrition from years of self-neglect, prescription.

While the creation of abstract art demands high intellectual capacity, Willem de Kooning, nonetheless, continued to paint prolifically. During the 1980s, de Kooning managed to produce almost a painting per week, which was a significant increase from his notoriously slow working pace during his peak fame in the 1950s. Some suggest that this change in productivity was a conscious decision by de Kooning to be less self-critical. However, the scientists believes that the decision was intuitive, driven by a desire to combat the increasing disorientation and inward turning commonly observed in individuals with dementia.

While de Kooning resumed painting, he placed his confidence in his new studio assistants, and embraced alterations in his approach, his artworks became carefree, exuberant, and paintings were finished in weeks instead of months. And his later paintings adopted a more minimalistic style, resembling haikus and invoking allusions rather than explicitly conveying meaning. As his Alzheimer's disease advanced, his art became increasingly abstract, with later works consisting of shapeless color sheets, lines and clean bands of vivid color mostly consists of red, yellow and blue with occasional touches of complementary violet, orange and green. At that point, the significance of de Kooning's paintings from the 1980s is a subject of debate, as they underwent a transition towards cleanliness, simplicity, and graphic elements, while still hinting at the biomorphic lines present in his earlier works. The paintings from this period in the 1980s can be identified as distinct and diverging from his previous body of work and also subject to its possible relation with Dementia and Alzheimer's Disease.

Figure 2. Seated figure (male classical) by Willem de Kooning, 1939

figure 3. *Rider (Untitled VII)* by Willem de Kooning, 1985

R. Storr explains:

While the sometimes-visible underpainting was a vestige of his subtly modulated chromatic schemes of the previous two decades, the clean paint he applied over it was now radically different in character. Gone were the complex mixtures he would work out, transfer to color charts, and have made up in salad bowl- sized quantities for easy use. His studio assistants designed a metal-framed, rotating, hinged easel that made it possible for de Kooning, increasingly bothered by back pains, to turn his canvases by hand without lifting them ... de Kooning would often begin working on a fresh canvas in the upper right-hand corner².

de Kooning started asking his assistants to take photos of his work as it progressed. Eventually, they started filming him while he worked for long periods of time. There are several films of de Kooning in his studio during this period, showing him working diligently, sometimes without much direction from his assistants. To continue his practice of incorporating old images into new paintings, he began using an opaque projector to project fragments of his previous artworks onto the new canvas. So, he would then manipulate the images, either by reversing them or transforming them into something new.

R. Storr clarifies this process as:

Projection became a shortcut de Kooning used to circumvent his waning interest in drawing as a

² Storr R.: *Willem de Kooning: The Late Paintings, the 1980's*. San Francisco, CA: San Francisco Museum of Modern Art, 1996.

*separate activity. Indeed, by 1980, he had virtually abandoned the practice of drawing, as the very few works on paper that can be positively ascribed to the decade attest... Gradually, however, de Kooning even tired of blocking in the projected image and gave the job to his assistants, who, (starting around 1984 or 1985) on occasion were called upon to lay in the first coat of oil paint in the empty spaces between the charcoal lines before bringing the canvas up to the studio where the artist would take over.*²

R. Storr continues:

*For his part, Dr. Norman R. Relkin, director of the Memory Disorders Clinic and program coordinator of the Cornell Neurobehavioral Evaluation Program at New York Hospital, provided the following prognosis to art critic Kay Larson, who had inquired about de Kooning's case, "In Alzheimer's, the mind's faculties drop away in stages: first, memory goes, then other functions that are in neighboring regions of the brain, such as the parietal lobe, known to be involved in drawing and construction abilities, spatial relations, and mapping. Color perception, incidentally, is something preserved until quite late in the disease. On the other hand, orientation, size, perspective, motion, all those things are affected quite early in the disease."*²

Oliver Sacks, a renowned neuropsychologist, discusses the fascinating process of readjustment that occurs when a skill is lost. When the question whether individuals should be viewed based on what a disease has taken away from them or by how they have adapted and preserved certain aspects of themselves comes to minds, Sacks further quotes neuroscientist Gerald Edelman, who suggests that personal and artistic identity is shaped by ever-changing global mappings of neuronal activity in the brain. These mappings are unique to each individual and can be recalled or reactivated in an instant, even in cases of dementia. Sacks argues that in dementia, one's style, neurologically speaking, remains intact and can be preserved until the end.

and Storr continues:

That de Kooning's artistic energy was winding down and his periodic fixation on details was increasing is poignantly visible in the chromatic blur and whirling vortexes or in the heavily laminated arcs of many paintings made from late 1987 through mid 1989. Such hypnotic repetitions and perseverations are indeed symptomatic of neurological disorder...de Kooning eventually lost the ability to make the space-expanding gestural leaps that had been the essence of his art. In the months before Elaine's death in February, 1989, when she was in and out of the hospital and away from de Kooning's studio, Lisa de Kooning, the artist's daughter, instructed the assistants to put a fresh canvas on the easel without projecting a drawing onto it. After some hesitation, de Kooning inscribed a target-like set of concentric circles near the middle and then reiterated them in an automatic motion. Several days later, he returned to the painting and did the same in the upper right-hand corner. Sometime after that he again approached the canvas and brushed a crisp, multi-colored arabesque that might have been lifted whole, like a jigsaw

puzzle piece, from a painting of the 1940s or 1950s. That was all. Between the first shape and the last lie extremes of compulsive activity and alert shape and muscle memory, but without the linear connective tissue he could not dynamically associate them sufficiently to stimulate further invention.

De Kooning's late paintings have a fuzzy quality that his friends and family believe was intentionally created through a change in his artistic process. During this stage of his career, he alternated between creating delicate and bold paintings. Some critics suggest that he painted in a trance-like state towards the end. Known for his intuitive style, de Kooning often claimed that if he knew where he was going with a painting, he was on the wrong path. The disease he suffered from involves a gradual decline with occasional moments of clarity. However, despite losing his memory and ability to speak, de Kooning's strong connection to painting allowed him to focus on his artwork. As he says in those famous lines *"I don't paint to live, I live to paint."*

References:

- Cipriani G, Cipriani L, Danti S, Picchi L, Di Fiorino M. Links Between Painting and Neurology: The Example of Dementia. *American Journal of Alzheimer's Disease & Other Dementias*®. 2019;34(4):217-222. doi:10.1177/1533317519826293
- SchottGD. Pictures as a Neurological Tool: Lessons from enhanced and emergent artistry in brain disease. *Brain*. 2012;135(pt 6): 1947-1963.
- Miller BL, Boone K, Cummings J, et al. Functional correlates of musical and visual talent in frontotemporal dementia. *Br J Psychiatry*. 2000;176:458-463.
- Gretton C, ffytche DH. Art and the brain: a view from dementia. *Int J Geriatr Psychiatry*. 2014;29(2):111-126.
- Cummings JL, Zarit JM. Probable Alzheimer's disease in an artist. *JAMA*. 1987;258(19):2731-2734.
- Maurer K, Pruculoli C. Paintings of an artist with Alzheimer's disease: visuoconstructural deficits during dementia. *J Neural Transm*. 2004;111(3):235-245.
- Mendez MF, Ghajarian M, Perryman KM. Posterior cortical atrophy: clinical characteristics and differences compared to Alzheimer's disease. *Dement Geriatr Cogn Disord*. 2002;14(1): 33-40.
- Mendez MF. Dementia as a window to the neurology of art. *Med Hypotheses*. 2004;63(1):1-7.
- Mell JC, Howard SM, Miller BL. Art and the brain. The influence of frontotemporal dementia on an accomplished artist. *Neurology*. 2003;60(10):1707-1710.
- Anauate MC, Bahia VS, Nitrini R, Radanovic M. Performance of patients with frontotemporal lobar degeneration on artistic tasks: a pilot study. *Dement Neuropsychol*. 2014;8(1):72-78.

- Harris JC. Excavation. *Arch Gen Psychiatry*. 2005;62(4):359–360. doi:10.1001/archpsyc.62.4.359
- Miller B, Cummings J, Mishkin F, et al. Emergence of artistic talent in frontotemporal dementia. *Neurology*. 1998;51(4): 978-982.
- Kedmy K: “Willem de Kooning: Moma.” The Museum of Modern Art, New York City, www.moma.org/artists/3213
- Rosenberg H de Kooning. New York, NY Harry N Abrams 1974;
- Stewart E G - Sage Journals, *American Journal of Alzheimer’s Disease and Other Dementias* Volume 17, Number 5, September/October 2002
- Storr R, Garrels G: *Willem de Kooning: The Late Paintings, the 1980’s*. San Francisco, CA: San Francisco Museum of Modern Art, 1996.
- Espinel CH. de Kooning’s late colors and forms: dementia, creativity, and the healing power of art. *Lancet*. 1996;347(9008): 1096-1098.
- Barker S, Barker R. *Neurology and Art: Willem De Kooning*. ACNR. 2010:30-31.
- Rankin KP, Liu AA, Howard S, et al. A case-controlled study of altered visual art production in Alzheimer’s and FTL. *Cognitive Behavioral Neurol*. 2007;20(1):48-61
- Siegal N. “Willem de Kooning: Late Paintings”: A Look At America’s Greatest Post-World War II Artist. <http://www.blouinartinfo.com/news/story/2654772/willem-de-kooning-late-paintings-a-look-at-americas-greatest> 2017. Accessed December 1, 2017.
- Tomkins C. De Kooning as melodrama: what do the late paintings really reveal? *The New Yorker*. February 10 1977:74-77.